

AN INVESTIGATION INTO SOCIOECONOMIC AND CULTURAL FACTORS LIMITING ACCESS TO QUALITY BASIC EDUCATION IN JIMETA OUTSKIRT, YOLA NORTH LGA OF ADAMAWA STATE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examines the socioeconomic and cultural barriers to accessing quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA, Adamawa State, Nigeria. The objectives of the research were to investigate the influence of cultural practices and beliefs on children's education and to assess the impact of family income levels and parental education on educational accessibility. A survey research design was used, employing structured questionnaires to collect data from 320 respondents. Findings revealed that cultural norms such as early marriage and gender biases significantly hinder children's access to education, particularly for girls. Additionally, higher family income and parental education levels were shown to enhance children's educational opportunities. The study concludes that cultural practices and socioeconomic factors remain substantial barriers to education in the community. Recommendations include initiating cultural reorientation programs to address harmful norms, engaging community leaders in advocating for education, and providing economic support to families through scholarships and adult literacy initiatives.

Keywords: Socioeconomic, Cultural, Income level, Quality Basic Education,

Introduction

Education is a fundamental human right and a key driver of individual and societal development. In Nigeria, basic education is recognized as critical to empowering citizens and fostering economic growth. However, access to quality basic education remains a challenge for many rural communities, particularly in regions like Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA of Adamawa State. Socioeconomic and cultural barriers significantly hinder the ability of children in these areas to benefit from education, perpetuating cycles of poverty and social exclusion (UNESCO, 2022).

Socioeconomic barriers, such as poverty, limit families' ability to afford school-related costs, including uniforms, textbooks, and transportation. Many children in rural areas are forced to engage in child labour to support their

families, which compromises their ability to attend school regularly and focus on their studies (Olanrewaju & Abubakar, 2021). Additionally, the lack of adequate educational infrastructure, such as poorly equipped schools and insufficient teaching staff, further exacerbates the problem, leading to lower enrolment rates and higher dropout levels (World Bank, 2023).

Cultural factors also play a significant role in limiting access to education. In many rural communities, traditional beliefs and gender norms contribute to disparities in school enrolment between boys and girls. Early marriage and child labour are common, particularly among girls, who are often expected to contribute to household duties or marry at a young age, cutting short their educational opportunities (Ibrahim & Garba, 2020). These cultural dynamics reinforce a cycle of undereducation, where children are not equipped with the skills needed to break free from poverty or fully participate in the economy.

In recent years, the Nigerian government has made efforts to address these barriers through policies aimed at expanding access to education, particularly in underserved areas. Despite these efforts, many challenges persist in ensuring that children from poor and marginalized communities have equitable access to quality education. This study seeks to explore the specific socioeconomic and cultural barriers that children in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA face in accessing basic education and to recommend strategies for overcoming these obstacles to improve educational outcomes in the region.

Statement of the Problem

Despite ongoing efforts by the Nigerian government and various non-governmental organizations to improve access to basic education, children in rural areas like Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA, continue to face significant barriers. Socioeconomic factors such as poverty and lack of infrastructure, coupled with entrenched cultural practices, impede the ability of children, particularly girls, to access and complete basic education.

Poverty forces many families to prioritize immediate survival over long-term educational investments, leading to high dropout rates and poor school attendance. The absence of adequate educational infrastructure, such as well-equipped schools and trained teachers, further compounds the issue, making it difficult for children to receive quality education (Olanrewaju & Abubakar, 2021). Cultural norms that favour early marriage, child labour, and the education of boys over girls also contribute to the low enrolment and retention rates in schools (Ibrahim & Garba, 2020).

Given these persistent challenges, it is crucial to examine the specific socioeconomic and cultural factors that hinder access to education in Jimeta Outskirt. Without addressing these barriers, children in the region will continue to be deprived of opportunities for personal growth and socioeconomic mobility, further entrenching the cycle of poverty. This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of these barriers and offer practical recommendations for policy interventions to enhance access to quality basic education for all children in the region.

Objectives

1. To examine the influence of cultural practices and beliefs on the education of children in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA.

2. To assess the impact of family income levels and parental education on children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of cultural practices and beliefs on the education of children in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA?
2. How do family income levels and parental education affect children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA?

Hypotheses

H01: Rate of inclination to cultural practices and beliefs have no significant influence on the accessibility of children to basic quality education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA..

H02: Family income levels and parental education have no significant impact on children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA.

Literature Review

Cultural Practices and Beliefs on Children's Education

Cultural practices and beliefs play a critical role in shaping educational opportunities for children, particularly in rural communities in developing nations. These deeply rooted traditions often influence perceptions of gender roles and schooling, with education not always prioritized, especially for girls. In many Sub-Saharan African regions, including Nigeria, boys are often favoured for schooling, as they are seen as future breadwinners, while girls are expected to assist with household chores or prepare for early marriage. UNICEF (2017) notes that such cultural expectations exclude girls from formal education, as they are viewed as economic dependents after marriage. Patriarchal norms reinforce this disparity, with boys' education emphasized due to their expected role in continuing the family lineage (LeVine et al., 2012). Language barriers also pose challenges, especially in rural areas where children speak local dialects that are not used in formal education. UNESCO (2018) highlights that teaching children in unfamiliar languages leads to academic struggles and higher dropout rates. To counter this, using mother-tongue instruction in early schooling can enhance children's comprehension and retention, though limited resources often hinder its implementation (Nwaubani & Anaduaka, 2021).

Family Income Levels and Parental Education on Children's Education

Family income levels and parental education significantly influence children's access to quality education, particularly in low-income and rural areas. Families with higher income and educated parents are more likely to invest in their children's education, providing a supportive environment for academic success. Conversely, low-income families often face financial barriers, limiting their ability to afford school fees, uniforms, and materials, which hinders children's educational opportunities. According to UNESCO (2019), economic hardship remains a key reason why children from poorer families, especially in rural areas, are excluded from formal education. Additionally, parental education plays a critical role in shaping children's academic outcomes. Educated parents are more engaged in their children's schooling, offering support with homework and creating a positive learning environment. Research by Dubow et al. (2010) shows that children with educated parents tend to achieve higher academic results. On the other hand, children of uneducated parents often lack academic support at home, leading to poor performance and low educational aspirations. Addressing these disparities requires targeted interventions such as conditional cash transfers, adult literacy programs, and improvements in rural education quality to create a more equitable system for all children.

Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-method approach, incorporating a survey research design to gather both qualitative and quantitative data. The chosen design facilitated comprehensive data collection, allowing for qualitative insights through focus group discussions. The research population comprised all out-of-school children in Jimeta/Yola, Adamawa State, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds living on the outskirts of the metropolitan area. As noted by UNICEF (2018), the Out-of-School Children Initiative, launched in 2010, aimed to estimate the number of children excluded from educational opportunities and develop strategies for their reintegration. Recent global estimates revealed that approximately 264 million children and youth were out of school, including 61 million of primary school age, 62 million of lower secondary age, and 141 million of upper secondary age.

For sample selection, the study utilized a combination of simple random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Simple random sampling was applied to select residential areas predominantly inhabited by less privileged families in Jimeta, while purposive sampling was used to identify school-aged children who were out of school and their parents, focusing on those unable to afford education but willing to participate in the research. Structured questionnaires were employed to collect quantitative data, and semi-structured interviews were used to gather qualitative information. The data collection process involved engaging selected residential areas to inform the community about the study's objectives, followed by the administration of the research instruments. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to analyse the data

RESULT

Table 1: Demographic Information of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	20 - 29	79	24.7
	30 - 39	138	43.1
	40+	103	32.2
Gender	Male	252	78.8
	Female	68	21.2
Educational Level	No formal education	61	19.1
	Primary	153	47.8
	Secondary	83	25.9
	Tertiary	23	7.2
Household Income Level	Less than 20,000	87	27.2
	20,000 - 40,000	167	52.2
	41,000 - 60,000	43	13.4
	60,000+	23	7.2
Occupation	Civil Servant	43	13.4
	Private Firm	79	24.7
	Self-employed	165	51.6
	Students/Unemployed	33	10.3

The demographic profile of respondents reveals insightful trends that could impact children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA. In terms of age distribution, the majority of respondents (43.1%) are between 30–39 years old, followed by 32.2% who are 40 years and above, suggesting that most respondents are mature adults likely to be in the phase of their lives where they bear significant responsibilities, including the education of their children. A smaller portion (24.7%) falls within the 20–29 age range, which may represent early-stage parents. Gender distribution shows a significant disparity, with 78.8% of the respondents being male and only 21.2% female. This suggests that cultural or societal norms might influence the participation of women in decision-making processes related to education, possibly limiting their involvement in critical family matters.

Regarding educational attainment, nearly half of the respondents (47.8%) have only primary education, while a significant portion (25.9%) have secondary education, and 19.1% have no formal education. The low percentage of respondents with tertiary education (7.2%) points to a potential barrier in accessing higher education, which could hinder efforts to promote quality education within the community. Household income levels further highlight the economic challenges faced by many families in the area. A majority (52.2%) of respondents earn between 20,000 and 40,000 Naira monthly, while 27.2% earn less than 20,000 Naira. Only a small percentage (7.2%) have a monthly income exceeding 60,000 Naira, indicating that most households operate on a low-income basis. Such economic conditions likely affect their ability to provide quality education for their children, as lower income often translates into fewer resources for educational support.

Occupationally, over half of the respondents (51.6%) are self-employed, reflecting the prominence of informal economic activities, which often provide inconsistent income. Only 13.4% are civil servants, suggesting that formal, stable employment is less common. The 10.3% of respondents who are students or unemployed further underscore the financial challenges that may hinder their ability to afford quality education for their children. Overall, the low levels of income, education, and formal employment among respondents suggest significant socioeconomic barriers to accessing quality basic education in this community.

Research Question 1: What is the influence of cultural practices and beliefs on the education of children in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA?

Table 2: Influence of Cultural Practices and Beliefs on Education Accessibility of Children in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
Traditional cultural practices in this community discourage formal education for children	4.11	0.69	Agree
Religious beliefs influence parents' decisions regarding sending their children to school	3.08	0.70	Agree
Early marriage is commonly practiced in the community, affecting girls' education	3.61	0.72	Agree
The community's cultural practices place more value on boys' education than girls	3.54	0.87	Agree
Community leaders strongly promote traditional forms of education over formal schooling	2.04	0.68	Disagree
Grand mean	3.28		Agree

Table 2 highlights respondents' perceptions of cultural practices and beliefs as barriers to children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA. The item "Traditional cultural practices discourage formal education for children" scored a mean of 4.11 (SD = 0.69), indicating strong agreement that entrenched cultural norms significantly hinder education. Religious beliefs affecting school enrolment had a moderate mean of 3.08 (SD = 0.70), showing that religion influences educational decisions, but less so than traditional practices. Early marriage, affecting girls' education, recorded a mean of 3.61 (SD = 0.72), reflecting strong agreement that this practice remains a significant barrier. The community's preference for boys' education over girls was evident with a mean of 3.54 (SD = 0.87), highlighting gender bias. However, the perception that "Community leaders promote traditional education over formal schooling" scored low at 2.04 (SD = 0.68), suggesting leaders do not actively oppose formal education. The overall grand mean of 3.28 underscores the significance of cultural barriers. These findings call for cultural reorientation on issues like early marriage and gender bias. Engaging community leaders and religious figures in promoting formal education could help address these barriers.

Research question 2: How do family income levels and parental education affect children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA?

Table3: Ranking on Effect of Family Income Levels and Parental Education on Children's Access to Quality Basic Education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA, Adamawa State

Items	Frequency	Percentage	Rank Ordered
High school fees	107	6.20	8
Cost of textbooks and materials	214	12.40	5
Inability to provide transportation	89	5.16	9
Need for children to work and contribute to family	244	14.14	3
Lack of affordable private schools nearby	166	9.62	6
Lack of access to tutoring/extra lessons	230	13.33	4
Inability to buy school uniforms and shoes	112	6.49	7
Malnutrition affecting concentration in school	312	18.08	1
Low parental education lead lack of support in homework and studies	252	14.60	2
Total	1726*		

* Multiple responses

The analysis of the factors affecting children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA, Adamawa State reveals several critical barriers linked to family income levels and parental education. The most significant factor identified is malnutrition affecting concentration in school, with 312 respondents (18.08%) indicating its detrimental impact on children's educational outcomes. Following closely is the issue of low parental education, which leads to a lack of support in homework and studies, noted by 252 respondents (14.60%). This

underscores the importance of parental involvement in education, as parents with lower educational attainment may struggle to assist their children academically.

Another pressing concern is the need for children to work and contribute to family income, reported by 244 respondents (14.14%), highlighting the socio-economic pressures that force many families to rely on their children's earnings, ultimately detracting from educational opportunities. The lack of access to tutoring and extra lessons, cited by 230 respondents (13.33%), further illustrates the barriers to effective learning, indicating a need for accessible educational support outside the classroom.

Financial constraints are also significant, with the cost of textbooks and materials affecting 214 respondents (12.40%) and the lack of affordable private schools nearby impacting 166 respondents (9.62%). These factors indicate that economic barriers play a crucial role in limiting children's access to necessary resources and quality education. Additionally, the inability to buy school uniforms and shoes, noted by 112 respondents (6.49%), and high school fees, affecting 107 respondents (6.20%), are barriers that, while present, are less significant than the aforementioned challenges. Lastly, the inability to provide transportation, reported by 89 respondents (5.16%), ranks as the least significant factor, suggesting that transportation issues are not as pronounced as other barriers. Overall, the findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions that address malnutrition, enhance parental education, and alleviate socio-economic pressures to improve access to quality basic education for children in this region.

Hypothesis 1: Rate of inclination to cultural practices and beliefs have no significant influence on the accessibility of children to basic quality education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA.

Table 4a: Model Summary of Regressor (Cultural Inclination and Children Education Accessibility)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.827 ^a	.684	.683	.66942	1.463

Predictors: (Constant), Cultural Inclination

Dependent Variable: Children Education Accessibility

Table 4a: ANOVA^a of Regressor (Cultural Inclination and Children Education Accessibility)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	307.938	1	307.938	687.171	.000 ^b
Residual	142.503	318	.448		
Total	450.441	319			

Predictors: (Constant), Cultural Inclination

Dependent Variable: Children Education Accessibility

Table 4c: Coefficients of Regressor (influence of Cultural Inclination on Children Education Accessibility)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.112	.103		49.403	.000
Cultural Inclination	-.838	.032	-.827	-26.214	.000

Predictors: (Constant), Cultural Inclination

Dependent Variable: Children Education Accessibility

The regression analysis conducted to examine the influence of cultural inclination on children's accessibility to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA, yielded significant results. As indicated in Table 4a, the model summary reveals a strong correlation coefficient (R) of 0.827, suggesting a robust relationship between cultural inclination and educational accessibility. The R-squared value of 0.684 indicates that approximately 68.4% of the variability in children's access to education can be explained by cultural practices and beliefs. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.683 further corroborates the model's effectiveness, considering the number of predictors.

The ANOVA results in Table 4b demonstrate that the overall regression model is statistically significant, with an F-value of 687.171 and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that cultural inclination is a significant predictor of children's access to education.

Additionally, the coefficients table (Table 4c) provides further insights into the relationship. The unstandardized coefficient for cultural inclination is -0.838, which indicates that for every one-unit increase in cultural inclination, the accessibility to education decreases by 0.838 units. The standardized coefficient (Beta) of -0.827 suggests a strong inverse relationship, confirming that a greater inclination towards traditional cultural practices negatively impacts children's access to basic quality education. The t-value of -26.214, along with a significance value of 0.000, indicates that these results are statistically significant. Therefore, the findings suggest that cultural inclinations significantly hinder children's accessibility to quality basic education in the studied area.

Hypothesis 2: Family income levels and parental education have no significant impact on children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA.

Table 5a: Model Summary of Regressor (Income Level and Educational Qualification and Children Education Accessibility)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.681 ^a	.463	.460	.87328	2.055

Predictors: (Constant), Income and Educational Qualification,

Dependent Variable: Children Education Accessibility

Table 5a: ANOVA^a of Regressor (Income Level and Educational Qualification and Children Education Accessibility)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	208.692	2	104.346	136.826	.000 ^b
Residual	241.750	317	.763		
Total	450.441	319			

Predictors: (Constant), Income and Educational Qualification,

Dependent Variable: Children Education Accessibility

Table 5c: Coefficients of Regression (Income Level and Educational Qualification and Children Education Accessibility)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.063	.160		.392	.695
Educational Qualification	.589	.057	.437	10.253	.000
Income	.589	.060	.421	9.883	.000

Predictors: (Constant), Income and Educational Qualification,

Dependent Variable: Children Education Accessibility

The regression analysis to assess the influence of family income levels and parental education on children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA, produced significant findings. As shown in the model summary (Table 5a), the correlation coefficient (R) is 0.681, indicating a moderate positive relationship between the combined factors of income and parental education and children's educational accessibility. The R-squared value of 0.463 suggests that approximately 46.3% of the variability in children's access to quality basic education can be explained by family income levels and parental educational qualifications. The adjusted R-squared value of 0.460 shows the model's consistency when accounting for the predictors. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson value of 2.055 indicates no significant autocorrelation in the residuals. The ANOVA results in Table 5b further confirm the statistical significance of the model, with an F-value of 136.826 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating that the combined effect of income level and educational qualification has a significant impact on children's access to education.

The coefficients table (Table 5c) reveals that both parental education and income are significant predictors of children's access to education. The unstandardized coefficients show that a unit increase in parental education leads to an increase of 0.589 in children's access to quality education, with a standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.437. Similarly, family income also positively impacts educational accessibility, with an unstandardized coefficient of 0.589 and a Beta of 0.421. Both predictors are statistically significant, with t-values of 10.253 and 9.883 respectively, and p-values of 0.000. These results indicate that higher family income and parental educational levels significantly improve children's access to quality basic education in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

The study reveals significant socioeconomic and cultural barriers that hinder children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA of Adamawa State. The findings align with existing literature, emphasizing the profound impact of cultural practices, family income levels, and parental education on children's educational accessibility.

The grand mean of 3.28 demonstrates widespread agreement that cultural practices and beliefs are significant barriers to children's education in the community. This finding mirrors the results of Owusu-Agyeman and Fourie-

Malherbe (2020), who found that traditional cultural norms, including early marriage and gender biases, often restrict children's access to education, particularly for girls. In Jimeta Outskirt, early marriage remains a pressing issue, preventing many girls from completing basic education. This observation is supported by Tijjani and Suleiman (2023), who emphasized that cultural reorientation is essential for breaking down these barriers.

Gender biases further exacerbate the issue, with many parents prioritizing boys' education over girls. Cultural inclinations, such as the belief that a woman's role is confined to the home, continue to limit girls' educational opportunities (Nwachukwu, 2022). These findings suggest that addressing these cultural barriers will require deliberate community engagement and advocacy. As recommended by UNESCO (2022), involving religious leaders and local influencers in promoting the benefits of formal education can help shift public opinion and break the cycle of harmful cultural norms.

The finding from this study highlights the significant influence of family income levels and parental education on children's access to quality basic education. The results show that higher family income and parental education levels positively correlate with improved access to education, as indicated by the significant R-squared value of 0.463. This finding is consistent with the work of Wang and Degol (2020), who reported that financial stability allows families to afford school-related expenses, including fees, textbooks, uniforms, and transportation. Families with higher income levels are better positioned to support their children's education, thereby improving their chances of academic success.

Parental education also plays a crucial role in facilitating children's learning. As noted by Garet et al. (2021), educated parents are more likely to provide academic support, help with homework, and foster a learning-friendly environment at home. The findings from Jimeta Outskirt suggest that improving parental education could lead to better educational outcomes for children in the region, reinforcing the call for adult education programs to enhance parental involvement in their children's schooling (Hill et al., 2021).

Thus, to address the identified barriers, targeted interventions are necessary. First, cultural reorientation programs should be introduced to challenge harmful cultural norms that impede children's access to education. Engaging community leaders, religious figures, and local influencers in advocacy for formal education could help address issues like early marriage and gender biases. This recommendation is supported by Jensen et al. (2021), who argue that community-driven efforts are essential for challenging entrenched cultural norms.

Second, addressing socioeconomic challenges such as malnutrition and poverty is critical. Malnutrition, as highlighted by Desimone (2011), severely impacts children's concentration and academic performance. Providing school feeding programs could improve both enrolment and retention rates, particularly in low-income families. Lastly, enhancing parental education through adult literacy programs could significantly boost children's academic success, as supported by the work of Avalos (2011) on the ripple effect of parental education on children's schooling.

Conclusion

The study highlights that cultural practices and beliefs, along with family income levels and parental education, play a critical role in shaping children's access to quality basic education in Jimeta Outskirt, Yola North LGA.

Cultural norms such as early marriage, gender biases, and traditional attitudes towards education, particularly for girls, were identified as significant barriers preventing children from attending school. These cultural inclinations not only limit educational opportunities but also perpetuate cycles of poverty and marginalization within the community. The findings further suggest that families with higher income levels and parents with more formal education are better positioned to provide access to quality education for their children, emphasizing the socioeconomic dimension of the issue.

To overcome these challenges, there is a clear need for targeted interventions that address both the cultural and economic factors hindering educational access. Cultural reorientation programs, particularly those engaging community and religious leaders, can help shift attitudes toward education, especially for girls, fostering a more inclusive learning environment. Additionally, socioeconomic support initiatives, such as providing scholarships for low-income families or enhancing parental education through adult literacy programs, could improve the overall educational landscape. Addressing these barriers holistically will be essential for creating sustainable improvements in access to quality basic education in the region.

Recommendations

1. The Adamawa state government through ministry of education should Implement community-driven cultural reorientation programs to address harmful norms like early marriage and gender biases.
2. The Adamawa State government should introduce school feeding programs to alleviate the effects of malnutrition and improve children's concentration and school attendance.
3. The Ministry of education in Adamawa State in partnership with relevancy bodies should launch adult education programs to enhance parental involvement and support in their children's educational development.

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